

The Transport Data Commons: operationalising FAIR data for global sustainable mobility transitions

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Abstract

Accessible and high-quality data are essential to the development of transport sector policy and investment pathways that can address urgent climate goals whilst providing equitable access to goods, services, and opportunities for diverse populations around the globe. Despite this importance, there are well-known and long-standing challenges in accessing data about transport systems and mobility, and in validating and advancing its quality and fitness-for-purpose. In this paper, we present the Transport Data Commons (TDC), an open global platform developed with the simple yet ambitious goal to make high-quality transport data accessible. We describe how the TDC infrastructure and governance of the TDC Initiative (TDCI) emerge from close consideration of access and quality challenges, and respond by enabling and operationalising work to make data FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. We outline the design of interfaces, open standards, tools, and community processes in the TDC, and describe how a commons approach offers benefits for people worldwide and the governments and development institutions that support them. In particular, shared and standard processes and infrastructure make the TDC a natural home and focal point for data-oriented work such as progress tracking for the UN Decade of Sustainable Transport, the sustainable development goals (SDGs), Sustainable Urban Mobility for All (SUM4All), climate assessment in the IPCC, and other efforts.

Keywords: Transport, data, sustainability, climate

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation and terminology

Transport of passengers and freight is directly linked to economic (e.g. employment and trade), environmental (e.g. greenhouse gas emissions) and public health (e.g. road safety and air quality) outcomes [1]. Future pathways for the transport system must deliver on urgent decarbonisation goals [2], whilst ensuring equitable access to goods, services and opportunities [3]. Transport, like any other sector, requires quantification of its current and historical conditions—based on the analysis of findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) data—to plan strategically for the future [4, 5].

We use the term “transport data” in the broadest and most inclusive sense. This includes all kinds of quantitative and qualitative information required to understand, evaluate, and shape the transport system. This includes, but is not limited to, data on vehicle fleets, infrastructure, travel demand, freight activity, fuel consumption, emissions (of air pollutants and greenhouse gases) and emissions factors. Transport data also encompasses transport-related policies and investments, geospatial data, service timetables, traffic counts, survey results and performance indicators, as well as emergent sources such as citizen-generated inputs (e.g. OpenStreetMap [6]) and remote sensing outputs (e.g. from satellite data). Increasingly, emphases on equitable transport planning make it essential to also capture data on informal transport services,

walking and cycling and accessibility to opportunities, particularly for marginalised populations and geographies. A wide conception of transport data is therefore necessary to address current gaps and develop transport sector pathways that directly address the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

By “*global* transport data,” we signify two things. The first is data sets that have truly global scope and coverage: not merely data for *some* populations,¹ but for all. Such data are necessary for systematic, consistent, and inclusive assessment of progress towards shared, global targets—especially on climate change. Secondly, ‘global’ signifies data that enable country, regional, and municipal policymakers everywhere worldwide to use suitable methods to support planning and action towards their particular policy goals. This is only possible if data can authentically reflect local conditions and context while, at the same time, being readily compatible with whichever analytical tools those authorities may choose to apply; and if both these features can be achieved without straining already-limited resources, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

In this paper, we introduce the infrastructure, governance, and ethos of the TDC as an open transport data platform. We detail the operation of the TDC, including processes for uploading and sharing data. Finally, we position the TDC as a natural progress tracker for the upcoming UN Decade of Sustainable Transport, and provide a set of next steps in operationalising the Commons for the mutual benefit of national and sub-national governments, developmental institutions, and populations worldwide. The paper proceeds as follows. The remainder of this introduction (Section 1.2) uses the FAIR rubric to structure a review of literature on barriers to accessible, high-quality data, and illustrate the gap that the TDC is intended to fill. In Section 2, we survey the existing landscape of providers of global transport data, their sources/databases/data sets, platforms, and tools for access, visualisation, and data application. Section 3.1 explains how requirements for TDC infrastructure and TDCI governance are derived from concrete user stories that link features and affordances with particular needs and benefits. Section 4 lays out the design of the TDC(I) intended to meet these requirements, and summarises progress on implementation. Section 5 looks forward to ongoing improvement of the Commons and unlocking shared benefits, including several ways that the TDC could be used as a ready-made system for collaborative work in support of global initiatives.

1.2 Barriers to FAIR global transport data

Historically, and to this day, producers and users of global transport data face numerous and persistent challenges in data accessibility and quality. Table 1 lists these common challenges, and organises them into 6 domains (technical, institutional, governance, political, equity, and environmental) and 10 subdomains. This categorisation is consistent with the FAIR principles for scientific data management and stewardship set out by Wilkinson et al. [7] in 2016: for example, ‘available’ and ‘interoperable’ align with the ‘technical’ domain. Recognising the value and clarity of the FAIR rubric, we

¹for instance, wealthy countries where official statistical systems, research funding, and private firms provide an abundance of data

Table 1 Common challenges and overcoming enablers in global transport data systems, categorised into six domains: technical, institutional, governance, political, equity and environmental.

Domain	Subcategory	Common Challenges	Examples of Enablers
Technical 	Data availability	Lack of data collection; missing modes or regions; proprietary restrictions	National travel surveys; vehicle registries; mobile data from apps or providers; mandatory data sharing
	Data interoperability	Incompatible formats; lack of metadata; siloed datasets	Standardised formats (e.g. GTFS); open APIs
	Data quality	Inconsistencies; noise; limited validation or ground truth	QA/QC protocols; verification methods; automated corrections based on machine learning
Institutional 	Capacity & resourcing	Skills gaps; high staff turnover; underfunded transport authorities	Trained analysts; funding for data initiatives
	Cross-sector collaboration	Fragmented mandates; lack of incentives for coordination	MoUs between transport, environment, and urban planning agencies
Governance 	Access & openness	Commercial restrictions; national security concerns; data hoarding	Open data policies; data commons models
	Accountability & transparency	Opaque decision-making; limited public access; tokenistic engagement with marginalised groups	Public dashboards; civic engagement
Political 	Leadership & vision	Political volatility; short-termism; low prioritisation of transport data	National digital strategies; support for open science; promotion of value of open data
Equity 	Representation & inclusion	Underrepresentation of informal modes, rural areas, and vulnerable groups	Disaggregated data by gender, income, ability, location
Environmental 	Climate relevance	Gaps in GHG estimation methods; misaligned metrics across sectors	Integration of emissions data with transport activity

expand the focus from solely ‘scientific’ data to all data produced and used in support of sustainable and equitable transport development and policy. We thus bring into scope and explicitly identify institutional issues, misaligned incentives, and other phenomena that are obstacles to useful data.

Data are produced and consumed via data provisioning *systems*; as such, they have systemic flaws that impact multiple FAIR criteria at once. Without any claim that challenges or enablers fit exclusively into one (sub)domain or another, we use the rubric here to organise discussion of these cross-cutting barriers and, based on the literature, we argue that these collectively prevent today’s global transport data from meeting needs.

Findable

Transport data is frequently either not collected or not made discoverable. This stems from weak incentives for data sharing, lack of capacity in public agencies, or proprietary control by private actors who perceive commercial risk in releasing data [8]. The data types included in this barrier are wide-ranging, from national government vehicle registration data (whilst many countries publish historical cumulative registrations, for instance [9], comparatively few publish data relating to on-the-road fleets, derived from, *inter alia* taxation records) to companies guarding crash statistics from autonomous vehicle driving data [10].

Accessible

Transport data is often only available from private companies, which limit access using with paywalls in order to generate profit. Even when public transport data exists, it

is frequently embedded in inaccessible formats: for example, travel activity data or fleet inventories are too often published as static tables within report documents (for instance, in PDF format), without accompanying machine-readable files. Institutional silos also inhibit access: city-level public transport authorities, for instance, may collect detailed operational data but lack the mechanisms, mandates, or resources needed to share it externally. Analysis of user feedback on open datasets by [11] shows that incomplete metadata and undocumented variables significantly hinder usability, particularly among non-specialist users. Goerge [12] highlights how legal constraints, such as ownership rights within state agencies, can restrict the sharing of state-owned data (which is generally highly relevant in the case of transport systems). Furthermore, the absence of standardised data retrieval mechanisms, such as APIs, limits integration with modelling tools. This constrains the data’s broader reusability and impact [13].

Interoperability

A lack of standard classifications across geographies undermines cross-country comparisons. One of the most persistent examples regards road vehicle fleet data: whilst official regulated vehicle classes exist in the USA and Canada based on gross weight [14], letter segments (A-F, J, M) in the EU are based on the size (volume) of vehicles, driven by markets with no strict categorisation [15]. The lack of a singular, global vehicle categorisation system is clear in sub-Saharan African markets, which tend to be driven by the majority importer of vehicles. As an example, the categorisations of four-wheeler passenger vehicle registrations can vary wildly: Kenya reports registrations of ”motor cars” and ”buses and minibuses” [9]; Ghana reports registrations in six categories [16];² Zambia reports only registrations of ”light passenger vehicles” and ”heavy passenger vehicles” [17]. This mismatch of categorisation in terms of vehicle weight (USA, Canada, Zambia), engine capacity (Ghana), vehicle volume (Europe) and vehicle use (Kenya) renders vehicle fleet data largely non-interoperable across countries.

Reusability

Data purchased from private organisations often comes with limitations on reuse and distribution to third parties. Even when data is shared publicly, it may lack the granularity, validation, or contextual metadata needed for meaningful reuse [18]. Crucially, under-representation of certain populations and modes reflects widespread equity concerns that hinder the reuse of data responsibly and inclusively. These include informal transport [19], often-disregarded transport modes such as walking [20], rural travel [21], and transport planning for under-represented populations [22].

Other cross-cutting barriers

One of the main challenges to FAIR data historically has been a lack of sufficient public funding for international institutions to collect, format, and maintain data sources with truly global scope. International organisations that do publish transport statistics,

²”private motor vehicles up to 2000 cc”, ”private motor vehicles above 2000 cc”, ”commercial motor vehicles up to 2000 cc”, ”commercial motor vehicles above 2000 cc”, ”private buses and coaches” and ”commercial buses and coaches”

such as the International Transport Forum (ITF) at the OECD, EUROSTAT, or the International Energy Agency (IEA) typically only collect, harmonise, and publish statistics from limited sets of member countries. This situation has led to gaps and unmet needs that have, in some cases, been targeted by private companies that offer cleaned, consolidated data for a price. However, such providers face few incentives for transparency about the original sources or quality of derived data. Consequently, new analyses too often require purchase or licensing of a new datasets, raising costs for public agencies and supporting organisations such as research organisations or development banks. Data users must do resource-intensive, costly work to adapt to individual data providers’ idiosyncratic choices of formats, application programming interfaces (APIs) and definitions.

1.3 Enabling and operationalising FAIR data

The Transport Data Commons arises in part from an identification of *enablers*: practices, conditions, and strategies that individually and/or collectively help to reduce or eliminate the challenges and barriers discussed above. Some examples and types of these enablers are listed in the final column of Table 1. It is critical to note that multiple examples of each type of enabler already exist. These collectively represent significant investments (one-time or ongoing) to create data sets, tools, dashboards, etc.; many of which we list in the following section. However, despite these efforts, the overall experience of data producers and users remains one of fragmentation: a coherent, FAIR whole has failed to emerge from the sum of many parts. This observation suggests that one or a few atomic efforts to add enablers—another dashboard, another ‘database’—will not be sufficient to achieve the goal of accessible, high-quality global transport data and its potential value for human development.

What is needed, we argue, is to *operationalise a commons*. By ‘operationalise’, we mean focused and cumulative efforts to build, sustain, and improve both governance and infrastructure that allow data producers to easily produce FAIR data, and data consumers to, just as easily, access and use it. The term *commons* is selected deliberately because it signifies openness, collective contribution, shared use and benefit, and other attributes that are essential to this effort (for an overview of the virtues of fostering the digital commons, see [23]). It also points to existing and successful digital commons efforts such as the Wikimedia Commons and Creative Commons.

The TDC offers a potential open-source solution that can improve the quality and transparency of data and help to reduce the data costs for research organisations and actors by sharing data across the ecosystem. Publicly-funded institutions can play an active role in reducing future data costs by requiring that data collected and used for project planning and delivery be shared via the TDC at an appropriate stage. With the agreement of private data providers, it may even be possible to publish analysis results based on proprietary data, provided that these results are shared in aggregated form on the TDC platform. The Global Fuel Economy Initiative [24] is one example of this approach.

The Transport Data Commons *Initiative* (TDCI, described further in Section 4.1) [25] seeks to formalise this platform and a set of processes for sharing and accessing transport data to enable (i) the development of robust, data-backed pathways towards

clean, equitable and resilient transport futures; and (ii) the tracking of progress towards transport-based and transport-adjacent SDGs. Another key aim of the TDCI is to support capacity building in data-sharing and use, particularly in low- and middle-income country (LMIC) contexts where institutional or technical constraints may limit the availability and interoperability of transport data. By providing open tools and guidance [26], the TDCI seeks to empower a wider range of actors—including subnational governments, NGOs and civil society groups—to contribute data, apply it in planning, and effectively record progress over time.

2 The existing transport data landscape

Efforts to aggregate, share, and visualise transport data have proliferated in recent years, reflecting a growing recognition of the critical role of data in building sustainable transport pathways. However, these initiatives remain highly fragmented across geographies and governance models. In this section, we list an illustrative subset of past and ongoing efforts to improve transport data quality and accessibility, focusing on three categories: existing data platforms (Section 2.1); tools and web interfaces (Section 2.2); and data providers (Section 2.3). This review informs the development of the Transport Data Commons by highlighting successful practices and persistent gaps in the current transport data landscape.

Terminology

Data stakeholders use a variety of terms to refer to their activities and the objects of their work. These uses are not always consistent, which can lead to confusion. Here we give a brief description of the terms (in italics) used in this section and paper.

Data are structured qualitative or quantitative values for a given *measure* (also called an indicator, metric, or quantity). A *data set* is a collection of data with consistent (often a single) structure. *Metadata* are of two kinds: *structural metadata* that describe the structure of data (or data sets): what is measured, dimensions, the units of measure, etc. and *process metadata* that describe how, why, by whom etc. data were produced; both may be stored and exchanged in the absence of data itself. *(Meta)data* is shorthand for “data and/or metadata.” (Meta)data can be stored in computer files that have particular *formats*; the structure and provenance of the (meta)data are distinct from the format in which they are expressed.

A *data provider* is an entity (person, organisation, or organisation unit) that provides (meta)data. A *data consumer* is an entity that accesses and uses (meta)data. A provider may be the originator of (meta)data, or may simply publish what it receives from another provider, with or without modifications; thus any entity may be at once a data consumer *and* provider. Entities stand in *upstream* and *downstream* relationships to one another, and there may be several entities between a ‘original’ *producer* of data and its ‘final’ user(s).

Tools is a broad, inclusive term for all technologies (especially computer software) used to work with (meta)data. Each tool affords (or not) its users the capability to take certain actions with respect to (meta)data, including find, access, limit/control/request access, select/filter, retrieve, publish, change formats, transform, visualise

(plot, graph, tabulate), etc. These direct affordances in turn support more complex actions and workflows associated with verbs like ‘analyse’, ‘harmonise’, ‘understand’, etc. Software tools may be either *free software* (“open source”) or *proprietary*; either type (and any (meta)data available through it) may be free to use or subject to access control.

Many tools are *web-based*, meaning the actions are accomplished through a graphical *user interface* in a web browser. A *database* is a system to store and retrieve (meta)data. A *data source* is a system that ≥ 1 providers use to provide access to ≥ 1 (meta)data sets. A *platform* may combine multiple features and affordances, such as finding, accessing, and visualising data. Tools may be *automated* or *manual* according to the amount of human involvement in their use, and multiple tools may be connected in *processes* and *workflows* that are more or less repeatable.

2.1 Databases and data platforms

A variety of platforms have emerged to consolidate transport data, from official statistical efforts to open community-led repositories. Notable among these is DigitalTransport4Africa [27] which, together with Datum.la [28], offers GTFS data and maps from over 20 cities in Africa and Latin America via an open GitLab repository. This initiative, coordinated by the Agence Française de Développement (AFD) and the World Resources Institute (WRI), exemplifies a decentralised, open-data approach to transport system mapping.

In the field of emissions modelling and life-cycle analysis, Ecoinvent [29] provides a subscription-based database of life-cycle inventory data, widely used in transport and energy research. iTEM Open Data [30], developed by participants in the International Transport Energy Modeling (iTEM) consortium, offers harmonised transport data using the SDMX standard, pulling from various international datasets. The Handbook of Emission Factors for Road Transport (HBEFA) [31] provides transport GHG and pollutant emission factors for selected regions; while an expert version is subscription-based, a simplified public version is freely available.

Global trade and economic modelling efforts, such as the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) [32], also include transport-relevant data, though typically with subscription-based access. Similarly, the Mobility Database Catalog [33], coordinated by MobilityData, provides standardised GTFS datasets across multiple geographies and is used by numerous transport applications and research tools.

Other platforms, such as the Sustainable Mobility for All (SUM4All) Global Tracking Framework [34], seek to monitor progress towards global transport-related goals, offering indicator-based datasets aligned with the UN SDGs.

2.2 Web interfaces, tools, and visualisations

Beyond static databases, a number of tools and interfaces have been developed to make transport data more accessible to diverse users. The OECD.Stat portal [35] is one deployment of the .Stat Suite platform, an open-source implementation of the SDMX standards, to enable efficient access to transport and other statistical data. Similarly,

the UN ECE Statistics Browser [36] provides comprehensive access to pan-European transport datasets, with tools for simple visualisation and download.

In the data visualisation domain, platforms like Our World in Data (OWID) [37] offer compelling web interfaces that enable non-specialist users to engage with data through interactive visualisations, often linked directly to source datasets. The IIASA Scenario Explorer [38] provides an example from the modelling community, enabling exploration of emissions scenarios, including those with accompanying transport measures.

The World Bank DataBank [39] and Eurostat [40] also provide extensive transport statistics through web-based tools that allow for visual exploration and downloadable formats, albeit with varied degrees of granularity and update frequency.

2.3 Data sources and providers

A wide array of institutions collect and publish transport-related data, either independently or in collaboration with others. The Asian Development Bank’s Asian Transport Observatory [41] is a regionally focused initiative offering publicly available datasets on fleet size, energy use, emissions and other transport-related indicators. Other multilateral efforts include the ITF statistics portal [42], which draws on common questionnaires developed with Eurostat and the UN ECE, and whose datasets are also accessible through OECD.Stat [35].

National and supranational organisations, such as Eurostat [40], OICA (Organisation Internationale des Constructeurs d’Automobiles) [43], and ACEA (European Automobile Manufacturers Association) [44], offer data on vehicle stocks, registrations and production. However, much of this information is either formatted for reporting (e.g. PDFs), is behind a paywall or lacks consistent time series coverage.

Additional specialised datasets come from technical institutions and research consortia. For example, the TRACCS project [45], funded by the European Commission, offers transport activity and emissions data for EU countries. COPERT [46] and the JRC IDEES database [47] support detailed emissions calculations across the transport sector. Remote sensing-based efforts such as TRUE [48] (led by the FIA Foundation, Bloomberg Philanthropies and ICCT) focus on vehicle-level emissions measurements, especially in urban settings.

Data providers such as the Global Fuel Economy Initiative (GFEI) [24] and the Transport Knowledge Base (TraKB) [49], curated by SLOCAT, contribute additional domain-specific insights, particularly in low- and middle-income country contexts.

Whilst these efforts offer valuable building blocks, they remain fragmented with respect to technical standards, access models, and spatial coverage. In domains other than transport, this is not the case: for instance, the Humanitarian Data Exchange (HDX) [50] operated by UN OCHA provides shared tools, standards, and recommended processes for many types of data used in humanitarian work. In transport, many initiatives exist offering only partial coverage or specific subsets of data (such as public transport, emissions, or vehicles) or regions, which limits their generalisability. This underscores the need for a unifying architecture, such as the TDC, that can bring together existing sources, enhance discoverability, and support standardised reuse.

3 Requirements for a Transport Data Commons

3.1 User stories: people and institution-based requirements

The development of the TDC has been shaped by a deliberate, structured analysis of prospective users and their needs when interacting with transport data. A series of representative *user stories* was developed to reflect the diversity of anticipated users, inclusive of both data consumers (such as researchers, policy analysts, civil society organisations, and business actors) and data providers (ranging from individual researchers to multilateral institutions to modelling consortia).

These user archetypes vary substantially in their technical proficiency, subject expertise, frequency and mode of access, and preferred data outputs that fit their specific needs. For instance, some users require only high-level summaries or visualisations for strategic or advocacy purposes, while others need automated access (via APIs) to highly disaggregated data for modelling and analysis. Importantly, the ability to reuse and interpret data responsibly also depends on the availability of clear methodological documentation and metadata—features that are especially crucial for high-frequency users and scientific contributors.

Table 2 presents an overview of eight user types identified during the TDC’s design process. These include, for example, a local NGO analyst estimating emissions from a bus rapid transit project, a doctoral researcher building global emissions models, and an e-mobility entrepreneur evaluating market opportunities. On the provider side, actors include a regional development bank wanting to share traffic survey data, a researcher sharing emission factor datasets, and an international modelling team seeking to harmonise multiple sources via an API.

The diversity of use cases in Table 2 underscores three key system requirements for a Transport Data Commons. The TDC must:

1. **Support both graphical and programmatic interfaces**, including standardised APIs.
2. **Accommodate users with limited technical capacity** through user-friendly web tools, while also ensuring that **advanced users** can efficiently interrogate provenance and underlying assumptions.
3. **Handle a wide range of data types**, for instance data that have been observed directly, estimated, or modelled; and allow to clearly track and distinguish their origins and methodological status.

For the web user interface flowcharts such as Figure 1 (shown for the example of the NGO user type) were used to map access, clicks, and destinations, in order to ensure that the interface design supported the specific actions to be performed in each user story.

3.2 Synthesised requirements

While the user stories highlight the specific and diverse needs of individuals and institutions engaging with the Commons, they also point to a set of overarching

Table 2 User stories developed to set Transport Data Commons requirements

User Type	Tech Prof.	Subject Exp.	Frequency	Interface	Data Resolution Type / Output
Local NGO	High	High	One-off	View, Download	Raw Local data, Reference
Intl. Policy Analyst	Medium	Low	Repeat	View, Download	Raw Local, International data
PhD Student	High	High	Regular	API	Raw International data
Research Assistant	Low	Medium	One-off	View	Visualisation
E-Mobility Owner	Low	High	One-off	View	Raw National, Local data
Development Bank	Low	High	Repeat	Upload	Observed/ City
Researcher (Provider)	Medium	High	One-off	Upload	Estimated
Intl. Modelling Team	High	High	Regular	API	Both Global

design principles that cut across use cases. In this section, we describe nine synthesised requirements of the TDC. They are not tied to any single group of users but rather reflect the foundational conditions necessary for the TDC to be sustainable and effective. They define the baseline against which technical, institutional and governance choices should be made, ensuring that the platform can serve both immediate analytical needs and long-term goals of transparency, inclusivity and interoperability.

- 1. The TDC must be standards-based.** The TDC should not contribute the proliferation of competing and incompatible formats and APIs for (meta)data. Rather, it should study, select, and apply suitable existing standards, using criteria including maturity, stability, pre-existence of an ecosystem of well-maintained tools. Furthermore, it should promote understanding of these standards among data providers and consumers, and contribute to the advancement of standards.
- 2. The TDC must be free and open-source.** Software developed by the TDCI and participants for the TDC must not be proprietary. Rather, free and open source tools should be used: existing tools where these are available and are (or can be made) fit for purpose, or new software as necessary. TDC participants and users must be able to understand precisely how (meta)data is manipulated by TDC tools, and adapt them as needed or desired to suit needs that were not anticipated by the TDCI.

Fig. 1 Flowchart used to design TDC web interface to suit user requirements

3. **The TDC must actively contribute to capacity building towards best practices.** Data consumers and providers of all skill levels should have a selection of learning materials and training opportunities suitable to their needs, including language, internet connectivity, time zone, level of technical skill, etc. These should be provided through, *inter alia*:

- Complete technical and user documentation.
- Video and other materials explaining HOWTO accomplish common activities.
- Interactive fora and discussion venues allowing asynchronous question-and-answer help.
- Synchronous and passive training workshops and other activities.

This documentation should be continually updated to align with current TDC process and tool features; translatable; and free for users to adapt and expand to suit their needs.

4. **The TDC must be community-led, transparent and adaptable.** Choices made by TDCI participants in handling data *must* be documented and added to metadata. For example, if TDCI participants choose to relabel or restructure original data from an upstream source, the exact nature of the change must be visible to data consumers, who must also be able to access ‘raw’ or unmodified data if they view this as a better fit for their purposes. Where the TDCI ‘harmonises’ data from multiple sources, structures, measures, dimensions, and categorisations, the choice of common structures must likewise be transparent; made in consultation with the community of users; and where possible configurable.

5. **The TDC must promote equity and representation.** The TDC should actively address gaps in data coverage for under-represented geographies, populations and modes, including informal and non-motorised transport, rural mobility, and accessibility data for marginalised groups.
6. **The TDC must provide clear provenance and quality assurance.** All datasets should be accompanied by metadata on provenance, collection methods, and validation processes. Where data are incomplete, estimated, or derived from models, this should be explicitly flagged, enabling responsible reuse and appropriate interpretation by users.
7. **The TDC must embed privacy and ethical safeguards.** In line with international best practices, the TDC must ensure that personally identifiable or sensitive information is protected. Ethical considerations should be embedded in data sharing processes, particularly where citizen- or community-generated data are involved.
8. **The TDC must be interoperable with external systems.** The platform should enable integration with existing data ecosystems through interoperable APIs and exchange formats, in order to avoid duplication, reduce barriers to entry and promote widespread uptake.
9. **The TDC must be designed for sustainability and good governance.** The TDC should establish clear governance structures that balance the interests of governments, civil society, researchers and private sector actors. Long-term financial and institutional sustainability should be built into its operating model to ensure continuity and resilience.

4 Building the Transport Data Commons

4.1 Genesis and governance

The Transport Data Commons Initiative evolved from a workshop on the sidelines of the 2022 annual International Transport Forum (ITF) Summit in Leipzig, DE, convened by the German Agency for International Cooperation (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit, or GIZ). It has since evolved into an informal, “birds-of-a-feather” working group with substantial involvement from a broad variety of stakeholders in global transport data: international governmental organisations (IGOs) such as the UN Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE); international non-governmental organisations (NGOs) such as the Partnership on Sustainable, Low-Carbon Transport (SLoCaT); multilateral development banks such as the Asian Development Bank (ADB); academic and research institutions such as the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) and the University of Strathclyde; development cooperation agencies such as GIZ and the UK Foreign Commonwealth & Development Office (FCDO); and private sector companies in transport and technology such as Ricardo AEA. A full list of participating stakeholders is available at [25]. These stakeholders represent or serve the interests of producers and consumers of global transport data, thus in turn the people, governments, and agencies who work on sustainable transport development and for whom that data is a critical resource.

Fig. 2 Architecture of the TDC technical infrastructure. Grey arrows indicate (meta)data flow. Data (ovals) and metadata (clipped boxes) are coloured by source: existing or upstream sources (green), direct submission by TDC users (blue), and derived/generated data from TDC data processes (orange).

The participants have organised into two working groups, a “strategy group” focused on the resourcing of TDC development of work and institutionalisation of TDCI, and a “data group” responsible for design and construction of the TDC tools and infrastructure, and coordinating data work from directly-engaged organisations. Members of both groups engage in outreach to further stakeholders, including current and potential TDC contributors and users: the “strategy group” focusing on large and institutional data providers and users, and the “data group” on individual data workers within or separate from these organisations. These interactions take a variety of forms, including regular open meetings, public discussion fora, webinars, presentations at transport- and climate-related events, and informal conversations.

The direct experience and outreach of TDCI participants informs the shared understanding of the existing transport data landscape, and the user stories and requirements outlined above. Regular and continued communication enables this understanding to evolve as the TDC user base expands, ensuring new user needs are captured, prioritised, and addressed.

4.2 Technical infrastructure and the TDC Portal

Figure 2 summarises the technical infrastructure TDC. The infrastructure is comprises a set of tools that together provide the features described in Section 3.1.

TDCI participants identified and contracted the construction of a “TDC Portal” [51]. This portal consists of two parts: first, an instance of the CKAN (Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network) data catalogue software, with supporting database [52].

CKAN is a free and open-source software widely adopted across governments, international organisations, and research initiatives. The TDC CKAN instance is customised with a metadata model that aligns with best-practices use of SDMX (next section). This serves the role of the “TDC (meta)data repository” in Fig. 2. The second part of the portal is a custom front-end that provides a user interface tailored to TDC users, serving the roles of “browser download”, “metadata catalogue”, and “explore & visualise” from the architecture.

Together, the portal provides an entry point for both data producers and consumers, and guides and assists them in data publishing and access practices that align with the FAIR principles. In particular:

- Metadata search, indexing, collections, and related conveniences allow data consumers to discover and engage with the scope and contents of data sets (F, A).
- Data are hosted and served free of charge (A). Users must create an account to submit records, but can access (meta)data without an account.
- Even for upstream sources that are access controlled, metadata records can be created that allow discovery of these data (F) and inspection of process metadata such as licensing terms.
- When authoring new records, users are prompted with explanatory text and help materials to submit metadata in standardised fields (I).
- Existing records can be edited based on user feedback, improving quality of metadata or correcting data errors (I, R).
- Records and data files may be accessed using the same API as all other CKAN installations (R).
- User accounts can be grouped by organisations, which each organisation having appointed editors and contributors.

On a more fundamental level, would-be data providers are able to use the TDC Portal free of charge, which saves them the expense and difficulty of setting up data-hosting infrastructure of their own. The TDC Portal also accommodates the varying levels of technical proficiency identified across the user profiles and stories in Table 2. Advanced users can quickly author multiple data records, while less proficient users can access the help materials and receive review input from organisation editors before draft records are published.

4.3 Standardisation and data quality via SDMX

TDCI participants identified and selected Statistical Data and Metadata eXchange (SDMX) as a reference framework for advancing data and metadata quality, interoperability, and reuse. SDMX is an international standard (ISO 17369 [53]) for describing, formatting, and exchanging statistical information, originated and maintained by organisations including Eurostat, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), and the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). In particular, the SDMX standards provide:

- A *information model* encompassing both data and metadata that is applicable to describe nearly any (meta)data structure, and to compare and align different structures.
- Precisely specified *formats* based on the common XML, CSV, and JSON file formats, for storage and exchange of both data and metadata. In particular SDMX supports storage, versioning, and exchange of both structural and process metadata independent of the data itself. The formats are both machine-readable and support human-readable presentation.
- *APIs* for publishing and retrieving data and metadata.
- Support for multi-lingual text in names and descriptions.
- A large and growing ecosystem of both free and proprietary tools, and documentation and learning resources, for users of various technical skill levels and needs.

Through adoption of SDMX and advancement of its use in the domain of transport and mobility, the TDCI avoids needless and duplicative work in describing and maintaining new data formats. Instead, TDC participants can focus on using the SDMX information model to structure discussions and consensus on common (meta)data structures and guidelines for their use, and then apply these to existing and new (meta)data in the TDC Portal. This ensures that data sets can be compared, combined, and reused across institutions and applications.

For one example, the Euro-SDMX Metadata Structure [54] provides a structure for metadata—specific fields such as “4.1 Data description” and “5.1 Frequency of dissemination”—such that every conforming metadata record will have a known structure with clear meaning and organisation. In the same way, the TDC CKAN instance helps users enter metadata in specific fields and formats that yield a common metadata structure across all TDC records. As a second example, the TDC can maintain (and regularly update) an SDMX “concept scheme” that includes items such as `VEHICLE_TYPE` (English: “Vehicle type”). Individual TDC records can be tagged with reference to this shared concept scheme, to express information like: “this data set has a `VEHICLE_TYPE` dimension,” “all data in this data set is for `VEHICLE_TYPE=‘MOTORCYCLE’`,” or “the labels for `VEHICLE_TYPE` in this data set are from this specific Ghanian list of codes/categories [also expressed in SDMX].”

4.4 Data processes: from public to harmonised data

In large-scale data collection, there exists an inherent trade-off between scope and quality. Assembling all known or accessible data can yield a “messy pile” or “data lake” containing very heterogeneous items that are unlikely to be interoperable or of well-understood quality. On the other hand, restricting records to only data that have been carefully curated or prepared to exacting standards can exclude exactly the records that some users may need or find useful.

To navigate this trade-off, the TDC is deliberately open to a diverse range of records and data set types, distinguished and clearly labelled according to extent of standards-compliance into four basic types, shown in Fig. 3 and described below.

Fig. 3 Four types of datasets are hosted by the TDC (L-R): public; community; formatted; harmonised. Image sourced from TDC [25].

Individuals and groups doing data work through the TDC can choose to focus supporting access, findability, or ‘breadth’ by adding more “public data” records—even if the quality is unknown or poor. Or, they can choose to improve quality/‘depth’ by manual and automated processing of particular records, moving them “up the chain” towards SDMX formats and the community-developed standards for “TDCI Harmonised” data. Both types of data work add value.

More detail on these four dataset categories is given below:

Public data

These consist of information sourced from public websites and other sources operated by data providers which may have no directly involvement with the TDC. These records are collated through TDC to improve accessibility. They can be published as metadata-only records with links to the upstream source, or may include data files, but these are mirrored exactly as originally published. Public data records help make these upstream sources findable by TDC users.

Community data

These consist of data sets submitted directly to the TDC Portal by data providers that may include civil society actors, researchers, or institutional partners. They may appear nowhere else on the Internet. TDCI participants in the role of “data editors” help these contributors to align their metadata with TDC standards but—as with “Public data”—data files remain in their original format, without validation or transformation. This category and process ensures low barriers to entry while maintaining the metadata consistency that makes these records findable.

TDC Formatted data

These consist of data that are in SDMX formats, either prepared directly by the contributor, or transformed from other formats via using TDC or other tools [26].

These records also contain, or point clearly to, structural metadata also in SDMX formats: for instance, code lists giving the labels used along every dimension in a data set. These records have higher quality in the sense that data consumers can access and interpret this structural metadata to directly understand the nature, provenance, processing, and meaning of the data. However, they have not been harmonised or necessarily undergone any quality assurance.

TDCI Harmonised data

These represent the highest degree of processing within the TDC. TDCI Harmonised datasets will be expressed in SDMX formats, with complete metadata, and will have been validated, converted to common labels for dimensions and codes, and where relevant, derived from multiple sources. (For an example of how this is done, the reader is referred to many datasets displayed on OWID [37].) Harmonised datasets offer a comprehensive and reliable basis for comparative or synthetic analysis, and are produced according to transparent methodologies and automated pipelines. They will be annotated with precise and complete information about exactly the nature of processing applied, allowing consumers to critically interrogate and help improve these processes.

As mentioned, one key aim of the TDC is to progressively advance datasets “up the chain” towards harmonisation. Whilst some contributors—such as multilateral development banks, national statistical offices in high-income countries, or well-resourced research consortia— may be capable of submitting records that are already TDC Formatted (again: as valid SDMX, categorised and with complete metadata), others may require support or may choose not to invest resources in this degree of standards compliance. The TDCI will actively collaborate with civil society organisations, local authorities, and government agencies in LMICs to build capability for (meta)data preparation and submission. This includes providing guidance, tools, and where feasible, technical assistance to embed standardised data management practices. In doing so, the TDC not only facilitates wider participation but also helps bridge structural inequalities in data representation and interoperability.

5 Next steps to sustain a thriving commons

As founding participants in the TDC Initiative, we call on other providers and consumers of (global) transport data to join in realising the potential of the Commons, enhancing its value as a public good and its utility for a growing scope of applications. This shared investment will help sustain the infrastructure and governance work necessary to keep the shared data resource and associated tools in good order, and expand them with planned and additional features. To conclude, we outline some of these benefits, future improvements, and potential applications.

5.1 Realise benefits of high-quality, accessible data

The TDC public goods can help reduce costs for data providers and data consumers. In particular, data providers can reduce costs in finding or developing hosting platforms

or solutions for their new data sets, devising metadata and data structures and standards, inventing file formats, developing software tools to write data to these formats, and ensuring that would-be users of their data can access, comprehend, and make use of their data. Data consumers can reduce costs in finding and accessing data, understanding its features and fitness-for-use, and transforming it from a large number of idiosyncratic formats. Critically, open TDCI processes allow data users and providers to contribute corrections, updates, and additions to existing records and data sets, improving their quality for their own and others' future use.

These costs reductions do not occur in isolation. Data providers and consumers are involved in important, labour-intensive transport analyses and assessment, supporting decision making with critical consequences for billions of people. When laborious data work is reduced or eliminated, and the available data for these analyses is of higher quality, people can redirect their efforts to more robust analyses, clearer communication of outcomes, and ultimately greater impact. It will be critical to collect and share stories of these benefits. As with the Creative Commons and Wikimedia Commons, as the scope and quality of TDC records grow, the total of these cost savings is likely to be significantly greater than the costs to build and maintain the infrastructure.

Several actions can help increase the magnitude of benefits. First, organisations and individuals can make in-kind contributions of time, or fund others, to expand the number of data sources reflected in the TDC Portal, with a particular aim of including data from non-OECD countries, which have historically been under-represented in data sets and data collection efforts. Second, mirroring the notion of open data mandates, publicly-funded organisations and those involved in development activities can incentivise the sharing of data via the TDC through project requirements. For example, all data collected or improved as part of a development project should be shared, either directly as “Community data” or “TDC Formatted data”, or first published elsewhere and then mirrored as a “Public data” record. Third, researchers can adopt TDC standards for SDMX formats and metadata, even for work in progress; this ensures that when data supplements to research works are published, they can be easily and directly harmonised with similar data from other sources.

5.2 Support global mobility initiatives

New international policy agreements and goals often prompt, or directly include, related efforts to collect, track, and analyse relevant data as a key input to assessment of progress. The UN Sustainable Development Development goals and the UN FCCC Paris Agreement are two examples. While it is critically important for stakeholders in these activities to agree on *what* should be tracked—that is, the specific quantitative measures, data structures, methods of measurement, and associated statistics—the creation of new formats, platforms, and interfaces can worsen the problem of fragmentation, making it unclear how new data relate to existing data in other locations.

The Transport Data Commons offers a natural alternative to this pattern. In particular, by adopting the TDC approach to standardised data formats, new data efforts can ensure “day-1” interoperability with existing tools. By exchanging data through

the TDC Portal or associated APIs, the cost and delay of establishing new data provision infrastructure is removed. There are multiple upcoming opportunities where such benefits could accelerate important actions.

UN Decade of Sustainable Transport

UN Member States adopted resolution A/78/148 “Strengthening the links between all modes of transport to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals,” which requested the UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs (DESA) to develop an Implementation Plan for the UN Decade of Sustainable Transport (2026–2035) [55]. Critically, this will involve provision for monitoring and progress tracking.

Since SDMX is already used and supported by several UN bodies—including the UN Statistics Division, UNICEF, and UN DESA’s own Interagency Expert Group on the SDGs [56]—TDC infrastructure offers a ready and compatible avenue for data-sharing associated with the Decade.

SUM4All

Since 2017, the Sustainable Urban Mobility for All [57] consortium has served as an important forum for articulating, advancing, and tracking a vision for sustainable mobility—focused on four pillars of universal access, efficiency, safety, and green(-ness)—as a catalyst for addressing other global issues. Its data-related outputs have included a “Global Tracking Framework” [34], a collection of measures recommended for measuring progress. The organisation in 2024 announced a shift to a “phase 2.0,” in which this tracking activity continues as a complement and input to UN Decade activities [58].

Climate assessment in IPCC AR7

In the middle of the above efforts, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) will produce its Seventh Assessment Report (‘AR7’) in roughly 2028 [59]. As with AR6, the Working Group III report on “Mitigation of Climate Change,” will include a chapter on transportation. IPCC authors must assess a large volume of peer-reviewed scientific literature; where this literature comes with data on projected transport emissions and scenarios of emission reduction, their work must include harmonisation of data from the same idiosyncratic formats that TDC data quality processes address. Researchers who (perhaps with the encouragement of IPCC authors) publish their data through FAIR formats and mechanisms such as the TDC will improve the likelihood that their work and insights are reflected in the assessment.

5.3 Advance tools, governance, processes

Section 4 outlined the current TDC tools and processes and TDCI governance, along with the overall architecture envisioned to meet the needs analysed in Section 3.1 and overcome the challenges outlined in Sections 1.1 and 2.1. Even as parallel efforts in data work (both coordinated and uncoordinated) improve the actual (meta)data in commons, several areas of work could help to advance the affordances and thus the usefulness of the tools and community as a whole.

In order to move existing and new records “up the chain” to higher degrees of standardisation and quality, both tools and community processes can be improved. The “TDC tools” software can be expanded with features to transform a wider variety of input formats, provide more user assistance in (meta)data preparation and validation, and to increasingly automate and chain data publishing steps into complete pipelines. These could, for instance, reduce or entirely eliminate work in checking upstream sources linked to TDC records for new or revised data inputs. Community processes could include discussion and agreements on lists of quality criteria for different categories of data. For example, community members with relevant expertise could be asked to identify markers of good and poor quality in data measuring vehicle sales and stocks, which could then be expressed as reusable code applicable to all current and new data for these measures.

Better tools for *data visualisation* are a common user request, but development of all-purpose visualisation solutions is extremely costly. TDC users can be supported through (a) documenting ways to feed TDC Formatted and TDC Harmonised data into mature and powerful tools in the existing data science ecosystem, (b) identifying existing modules for data visualisation that can be integrated with the TDC Portal, (c) enabling user-to-user sharing of examples and experiences with visualising TDC data sets.

Finally, as the TDCI grows, transparent and accountable decision-making, use of resources, and responsiveness to community needs will be critical. The TDCI can pursue *institutionalisation*, with an eye to how other, similar organisations managing digital commons and public goods have formalised their structures in order to meet the same goals.

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